

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 6, 30 Июнь

BUXORO MADRASALARI

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti “Tarix va filologiya” kafedrasi Tarix fani o’qituvchisi
Toshpo’latova Shaxnoza Shuhratovna

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Buxoro madrasalari — Turon hududiga islom kirib kelib, mustahkam o‘rnashganidan so‘ng, Buxoro vohasida IX asr boshlaridan tashkil etila boshlagan oliy ta‘lim berish uchun maxsus qurilgan o‘quv binolari — oliy o‘quv yurtlarining umumlashtirilgan nomi haqida shuningdek, ularda ta‘lim olgan ulamolarning diniy masalalardagi fikrlari Misr va Hijozda o‘qiganlarning fikrlaridan ko‘ra mo‘tabarroq hisoblangan haqida ma‘lumotlar bayon etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar. Madrasa, islom dini, Abdullazizxon madrasasi, me‘morchiligi, Mimxoqon ibn Xo‘ja Muhammadamin, saroy me‘mori Muhammad Solih, masjid naqshlarini ishlagan koshinkor usta Xo‘ja Muhammad Amin o‘g‘li Mimxoqon, xattot Mavlono Muhammad Amindir.

MADRASAS OF BUKHARA

Abstract. This article describes the general name of Bukhara madrasahs - the general name of Bukhara madrasahs - educational institutions built specifically for providing higher education in the Bukhara oasis from the beginning of the 9th century, after the introduction of Islam to the territory of Turan, as well as the opinions of scholars who studied in them on religious issues in Egypt and Hijaz. The information is stated to be more reliable than the opinions of the readers.

Key words. Madrasah, Islamic religion, Madrasa of Abdullaziz Khan, architecture, Mimkhaqan ibn Khoja Muhammadamin, palace architect Muhammad Salih, master tiler Khoja Muhammad Amin, son of Mimkhaqan, calligrapher Mawlana Muhammad Amin.

МЕДРАСЕ БУХАРЫ

Абстрактный. В данной статье описывается общее название бухарских медресе - общее название бухарских медресе - учебных заведений, построенных специально для предоставления высшего образования в Бухарском оазисе с начала 9 века, после введения ислама на территории Турана, а также как и мнения обучавшихся в них учёных по религиозным

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 6, 30 Июнь

вопросам в Египте и Хиджазе. Информация заявлена как более достоверная, чем мнения читателей.

Ключевые слова. Медресе, исламская религия, медресе Абдуллазиз-хана, архитектура, Мимхакан ибн Ходжа Мухаммадамин, дворцовый архитектор Мухаммад Салих, мастер-плиточник Ходжа Мухаммад Амин, сын Мимхагана, каллиграф Мавлана Мухаммад Амин.

Buxoro madrasalari nafaqat oliy o'quv yurti, balki o'ziga xos me'moriy yodgorlik obidalari ham edi. Buxoro madrasalari o'z hashamati, pishiq va puxta qurilganligi bilan me'moriy jihatdan o'rta asr arxitekturasining eng nodir namunalari sifatida hozirgacha saqlanib qolgan. Madrasalar qurish ishi bilan asrlar osha shug'ullanilganligi bois, bu borada boy tajriba ham shakllangan. Buxoro hududida bir qancha madrasalari bilan mashhurdir, shulardan biri Abdullazizxon madrasasi hisoblanadi.

Abdulazizxon madrasasi — Buxorodagi me'moriy yodgorlik. O'zbek hukmdori Abdulazizxon donatorligida bunyod etilgan. Saroy me'mori Mimxoqon ibn Xo'ja Muhammadamin tomonidan 1652-yilda qurilgan.

Memorchiligi. Qo'sh madrasa (bir-birga qarama qarshi qarab turadigan binolar majmuasi)ning janubiy tomonida joylashgan. Ulug'bek madrasasining (1419) qarshisida. Madrasa tuzilishi oddiy va hujralari ikki oshyonli. Madrasa to'rt tomoni markazida yirik peshtoqli uslubda qurilgan. Peshtoqlarning asosiy kirish qismi ikki tomonlama.

Umuman madrasa bezaklari yuksak san'at va mahorat bilan ishlangan. Katta peshtoq nafis va nodir koshinkori naqshlar bilan ziynatlangan. Islimiy naqshlar qatorida afsonaviy jonivorlar tasviri ham berilgan. Madrasa hujralari, ayniqsa, janubiy ayvon peshtoqi turli-tuman naqshlar bilan bezatilgan. Gumbaz shipining ganchli muqarnaslari orasida islimiy naqshlar va kundal uslubidagi bezaklar mavjud. Naqshlar, asosan, moviy rang bo'yoqlar bilan chizilgan. Asosiy o'lchami: atrof aylanasi — 50x67 metr, hovli — 28x35 metr. Madrasa XVII asr Buxoro mahobatli me'morligining yetuk namunasi.

Abdulazizxon madrasasi sirdan qaraganda Ulug'bek madrasasi kabidir: bu madrasa kompozitsiyasi ham uzunchoqroq bo'lib, old tomonining markazida ravoqli peshtoq, burchaklarida burj — guldastalar ishlangan, 2 qavatli yon qanotlar, kiraverishdagi xonalar va hovli chor atrofidagi 2 qavatli qator ravoqlar tizmasi ham

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 6, 30 Июнь

o‘xshab ketadi. Ammo, Abdulazizxon madrasasi yirikroq va murakkabroq loyihalashtirilgan. Yon tomonlarining markaziy qismi 2 qavatli hujralar bilan urg‘u berib, biroz tashqariga bo‘rttirib chiqarilgan va hovli kompozitsiyasi bilan peshtoq yordamida uyg‘unlashtirilgan. Burchaklardagi beshqirrali yo‘laklardan shu burchaklardagi bir qancha katta-kichik hujralarga o‘tilagan. Aql idrok bilan qilingan ish natijasida qurilish maydonining har bir kvadrat metridan to‘la foydalanilgan va XIV—XV asrlarga xos g‘isht terish uslubiga yangilik kiritilgan.

Shu bilan bir qatorda XVII asr me‘morlari tomonidan tom qismlarini yopishda hech qanday yangi konstruktiv uslublar topishmagan: aksincha, masjid, darsxona tepasi XV—XVI asrlardagi uslublardan ancha bo‘sh bo‘lgan gumbazlar sistemasi bilan yopilgan. Bu yerda 8 qirrali oddiy ravoqli shakllar va murakkab iroqi muqarnaslar bilan chambarchas bog‘lanib, ajoyib bezak kashf etilgan. Abdulazizxon madrasasining ahamiyati ham shundaki, u serhasham bezalib, Turon me‘morchiligida ma‘lum bo‘lgan hamma bezaklarning rang-barang uslublaridan foydalanilgan. Xuddi Ulug‘bek madrasasi kabi uning old tomoni hamda hovlidagi ayvon va ravoqlarga koshinli naqshlar ishlangan. Ammo... Bu koshinli g‘ishtlar juda rang-barangdir: sirsiz sopol g‘ishtlar ustiga ko‘k, zangori, oq parchinlar qoplangan. Lekin ular yangicha usulda, choksiz taxtachalar holida yerga — taxminga terilgan va ganch qorishmasi yordamida keyin devorga yopishtirilgan.

O‘yma sirli sopoldan ishlangan koshin bezaklar mavzui ham o‘zgargan. Dastlab rasm bo‘lgan mavhum o‘simliklar nusxasi o‘rniga mavzuida xayoliy jonivorlar tasvirlangan manzara qismlari paydo bo‘ladi. Bu XVII asr yodgorliklariga xosdir (Samarqanddagi Sherdor madrasasi peshtoqidagi yo‘lbars va Buxorodagi Devonbegi madrasasidagi afsonaviy qushlar tasviri). Bu madrasaning bosh peshtoqidagi koshin namoyonlarida ilon bo‘yinli afsonaviy qushlar va 2-qavatdagi timpanlarda quyoshga qarab uchyotgan afsonaviy qushlar. Naqqoshlar rang-barang koshin qoplamalarining badiiy ta‘sirchanligini yanada oshirish yo‘llarini izlashgan. Buni peshtoq chekkasida ilon bo‘yinli va boshi qushnikiga o‘xshash uzun dastali ko‘k guldon, koshin bezak ichidan ajralib ko‘zga yaqqol tashlanib turgan tasvirdan ko‘rish mumkin.

Avvalgidek ravoq timpanlarini sirli sopolli bezaklar qoplagan. Hovlidagi ayvon chekkalariga yozilgan yozuvlar — Qur‘on oyatlari naqshlarga aralashtirilib, ajoyib ko‘rinish hosil etgan. Bezaklar bir xil o‘lchamli (25x25 sm) sirli sopol taxtachalarga tushirilgandan keyin devorlarga har xil kompozitsiya asosida

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 6, 30 Июнь

yopishtirilgan. Abdulazizxon madrasasida xonalarning ichki bezagiga alohida e'tibor berilgan. Darsxona, qishki va yozgi masjid, 2-qavatdagi kutubxona devorlari ko'k rang zaminli zarhal bezak — xushmanzara kundal usulida tushirilgan bo'rtma naqshlar bilan bezatilganligi uchun xuddi ustiga zarbop yopilgandek bo'lib, boshdan-oyoq yarqirab turard. Bunda me'morchilikning har bir qismiga, qo'yingchi, muqarnaslarning eng mayda nusxalariga ham aniq qilib mustaqil kompozitsiya: yulduzsimon va boshqa shakldagi har bir bezaklar ishlangan. Darsxona devorlarida xitoy chinnisidagi bezaklarga o'xshatib ishlangan naqshlarni — oq zamin ustiga ko'k rang bilan berilgan ajoyib manzaralarni, daraxtlar orasiga qo'yilgan so'ri, bulut va suv oqimlari tasvirlarini ko'rish mumkin.

Mahobatli binolarning bezakli gumbazlari badiiy jihatdan ayniqsa qimmatlidir, ular tekislik bilan fazoga geometrik shakllar tushirish san'atining — Turon me'morlari mehr bilan yaratgan san'atning necha asrlik butun rivojlanish tarixini munosib ravishda bezab turgan tojdek bo'lib ko'rinadi.

Har tomonlama yetuk me'morlar o'zlarining takomillashgan tasavvurlarini san'atning noyob asarlari darajasiga ko'tardilar va qanday yuqori pog'onaga chiqqanini ko'rsatishdi. Gumbaz qubbasidagi iroqi muqarnaslar ravoqlar ichidagi taxta muqarnaslarga chirmashib, qo'shib ketganligi tufayli bu yarim qorong'i xonalar sharq ertaklaridagi hashamatli saroylarni eslatadi.

Madrasadagi hashamatli bezak ishlari to'la yakunlanmagan. asosiy peshtoq yonlaridagi muqarnasli qubbalar devorida yog'och qoldiqlari bor, aslida bu yog'ochlar qurilish tugaganidan so'ng kesib tashlanadi. Old tomonining o'ng qanoti va hovlining g'arbiy tomoni koshinsiz.

Mana shu hashamatli yodgorlikni bunyod qilgan me'mor va ustalarning nomlari ham ularning o'zi yaratgan bezaklar ichida zamonlar osha bizgacha yetib kelgan. Ular saroy me'mori Muhammad Solih, masjid naqshlarini ishlagan koshinkor usta Xo'ja Muhammad Amin o'g'li Mimhoqon, xattot Mavlono Muhammad Amindir. Ularning hammasi buxorolik bo'lib, yuksak darajada ravnaq topgan o'ziga xos mahalliy badiiy maktab vakillaridir.

Madrasa bizgacha asl holda yetib kelmagan. Buning sababi g'isht terishning o'ziga xos uslublari (devorlar 3 qat bo'lib, orasi g'isht va loy chiqitlari bilan to'ldirilgan) va tomdan tushgan hamda bino atrofida yig'iladigan yog'in-sochin suvlarining yo'qotishni to'g'ri hal etilmaganligidadir.

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 6, 30 Июнь

Yodgorlik me'morchilik bo'yicha mutaxassislar tomonidan to'la va mukammal o'rganilib, ta'mir ishlari uchun kerak bo'lgan masalalar ko'p yillar davomida hal etilgan. Arxitekturaviy, konstruktiv va arxeologik tekshirish natijasida arxitektura shakli va bezaklarini ta'mir qilish, qayta tiklash ishlarining loyihasi yaratilgan. Umumiy o'lchamlari 50x67 metr; to'g'ri burchakli hovli 28x35 metrlik sahni egallagan.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI.

1. Gadayeva Mohigul Muxamedovna. (2023). INNOVATSION TA'LIM-BUYUK KELAJAK POYDEVORI . *World Scientific Research Journal*, 17(1), 74–76. Retrieved from <http://www.wsrjournal.com/index.php/wsrj/article/view/2767>
2. Gadayeva , M. . (2024). ABOUT THE HISTORY OF THE VEIL OR MEDIEVAL WOMEN'S DRESS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 1097–1103. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/29537>
3. Universiteti, G. M. M. O. X. (2023). UCHINCHI RENESANS DAVRIDA AJDODLARIMIZ MEROSINI ORGANISH ORQALI INTEGRATSION TA'LIMNI YANADA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH TAMOYILLARI: ЧАСТЬ 1 ТОМ 1 ИЮЛЬ 2023 год. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 1(1), 11-16.
4. Gadayeva Mohigul Muxamedovna. (2023). HISTORY OF PATRIOTIC WOMEN . *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 3(12), 69–75. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijhps/Volume03Issue12-12>
5. Gadayeva, . M. . (2023). THE UNIQUE SIGNIFICANCE OF MASTERING SOCIAL SCIENCES DURING THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NEW UZBEKISTAN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 459–464. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/25292>
6. Gadayeva, M. (2024). EFFECTIVE WAYS TO USE THE "THOUGHTSTORM" METHOD ON THE THEME OF THE "EASTERN RENAISSANCE" ERA. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 1024–1027. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/28631>
7. Gadayeva, M. (2024). ATTACK ACTION. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 1028–1033. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/28634>

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 6, 30 Июнь

8. Gadayeva , M. (2023). ONE OF THE TIMURID QUEENS IS BIBIKHONIM. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(12), 749–754. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/27189>

9. Gadayeva Mohigul Muxamedovna. (2023). INNOVATSION TA`LIM-BUYUK KELAJAK POYDEVORI . *World Scientific Research Journal*, 17(1), 74–76. Retrieved from <http://www.wsrjournal.com/index.php/wsrj/article/view/2767>

10. Vahobovna, S. G. (2024). Canada during the world economic crisis of 1929-1933. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 4(4), 48-54.

11. Srojeva, G. . (2024). ATTENTION PAID TO PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN NEW UZBEKISTAN. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 258–266. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30750>

12. Srojeva, G. (2024). THE CANADIAN ECONOMY DURING THE GLOBAL ECONOMIC CRISIS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 57–63. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30678>

13. Vahobovna, S. G. (2024). Vahobovna, S. G. (2024). Role of Preschool Educational Institutions in Education of a Perfect Person. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4(3), 208-214.

14. Vahobovna, S. G. (2023). QUYI ZARAFSHON VOHASI TURIZM IMKONIYATLARI.

15. Srojeva, G. . (2024). STRENGTHENING THE MATERIAL AND TECHNICAL BASE OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTIONS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 673–681. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/29450>

16. Srojeva, G. (2024). INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 1041–1050. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/29547>

17. Srojeva , G. . (2024). SOLUTIONS, RESULTS AND PROBLEMS OF REFORMS IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 782–788.

18. Srojeva, G. (2024). EFFECTIVE FORMS OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION AND EDUCATIONAL WORK IN A PRESCHOOL

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 6, 30 Июнь

EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 247–253. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/29010>

19. Vahobovna, S. G. (2021). Khoja Abdulkhaliq Ghijduvani And Its Method. *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements*, 2(10), 39-40.

20. Gulbahor, S. (2023). CONTINUITY IN EDUCATION-CHIEF MEZON. *Modern Science and Research*, 2, 834-839.

21. Srojjeva, G. (2023). LOWER ZARAFSHAN OASIS TOURISM OPPORTUNITIES. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 199–204.

22. Srojjeva, G. (2023). CONTINUITY IN EDUCATION-CHIEF MEZON. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(12), 834–839. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/27238>

23. Vahobovna, S. G. (2024). YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM–TARBIYA MUASSASALARIGA QARATILAYATGAN E'TIBOR.

24. Vahobovna, S. G. (2024). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM MUASSASIDA MA'NAVIY-AXLOQIY TARBIYA VA MA'RIFIY ISHLARNING SAMARALI SHAKLLARI.

25. Vahobovna, S. G. (2024). TALIM SOHASIDAGI ISLOHATLAR ECHIMI, NATIJALARI VA MUAMMOLARI.

26. Vahobovna, S. G. (2024). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM–TARBIYA MUASSASALARI MODDIY TEXNIKA BAZASINI MUSTAHKAMLASH.

27. Srojjeva, G. (2024). TA'LIM SOHASIDA XALQARO HAMKORLIK..

28. Vahobovna, S. G. (2024). JAHON IQTISODIY INQIROZI DAVRIDA KANADA IQTISODIYOTI.

29. Toshpo'latova, S., & Tursuntoshova, S. (2024). KHOJA ABDULKHOLIY GIJDUVANI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 87–93. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30711>

30. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). ETHNOLINGUISTICS OF ETHNOLOGIES OF BUKHARA. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 1004–1011. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/29523>

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 6, 30 Июнь

31. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). ETHNOLINGUISTICS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 500–507. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/29386>

32. Toshpo'latova, S., & Jo'rayeva, M. (2024). HISTORY AND ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS OF JONDOR DISTRICT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 447–450. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/31046>

33. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). RELIGIOUS ANTHROPOLOGY. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 504–510. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/28281>

34. Shakhnoza Shuhratovna, T. (2023). M. S. ANDREYEV'S WAY OF LIFE. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769)*, 1(10), 655–659. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/STEM/article/view/2280>

35. Shuhratovna, T. S. (2024). Linguistic Anthropology. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4(3), 432–437. Retrieved from <https://inovatus.es/index.php/ejine/article/view/2792>

36. Toshpolatova Shakhnoza Shuhratovna. (2023). ETHNOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL COSTUMES AND RITUALS OF TAJIKS IN THE WORKS OF M. S. ANDREYEV. *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 3(12), 42–47. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijhps/Volume03Issue12-08>

37. Toshpolatova Shakhnoza Shuhratovna. (2024). THE PALACES OF THE BUKHARA EMIR. МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА, 2(5), 239–250. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11180855>

38. Toshpo'latova, S., & Xudoyqulov, S. (2024). HISTORY AND ETHNOLOGY OF OLOT DISTRICT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(5), 148–151. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/31951>

39. Toshpo'latova, S. (2023). M. S. ANDREYEV-SCIENTIFIC CAREER. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(12), 801–807. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/27191>

40. Sh.Sh.Toshpo'latova, & I.N.Naimov. (2023). M.S. ANDREYEV – O'RTA OSIYO XALQLARI ETNOGRAFIYASINING YIRIK

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 6, 30 Июнь

OLIMI. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(8), 1214–1222. Retrieved from <https://humoscience.com/index.php/itse/article/view/698>

41. Toshpulatova Shakhnoza Shuhratovna. (2023). ETYMOLOGY OF TAJIK MARRIAGE CEREMONY. *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 3(11), 17–23. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijhps/Volume03Issue11-05>

42. Toshpo'latova , S. S. (2023). TOJIKLAR MILLIY KIYIM-KECHAKLARI VA “BESHMORAK” MAROSIMINING ETNOLOGIK TAHLILI. *SCHOLAR*, 1(28), 395–401. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/openscholar/article/view/5071>

43. Naimov, I. ., & Toshpo'latova, S. . (2023). MARRIAGE CEREMONY OF TAJIKS IN THE WORK OF MIKHAIL STEPANOVICH ANDREYEV “TADJIKI DOLINI KHUF”. *International Journal of Intellectual Cultural Heritage*, 3(1), 12–16. Retrieved from <https://ihm.iscience.uz/index.php/ijich/article/view/205>

44. Toshpo'latova, S. (2023). ETHNOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF CALENDRIAL CALCULATION AND LENGTH MEASUREMENTS OF KHUF VALLEY TAJIKS IN THE RESEARCHES OF M.S. ANDREYEV. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 291–299. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/25092>

45. Toshpo'latova, S., & Ashurova, G. (2023). THE HISTORY AND DESCRIPTION OF THE WORK OF M. S. ANDREYEV - "ARK BUKHARI". *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 404–409. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24229>

46. Toshpo'latova, S. . (2023). A STUDY OF THE WEDDING CEREMONY OF THE TAJIKS OF AFGHANISTAN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 84–89. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/23903>

47. Toshpolatova Shakhnoza Shuhratovna. (2024). THE PRESENT IRANIANS. МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА, 2(4), 453–462. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10969477>.

48. Хасанова Шахноза Баходировна. (2024). РОЛЬ ИНТЕРНЕТ-СЛЕНГА В СИСТЕМЕ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 2(5), 235–243. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11455009>

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 6, 30 Июнь

49. Хасанова, Ш. (2024). ИСТОРИЯ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ПАРЕМИИ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЛЕКСИКОЛОГИИ. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(5), 1231–1238. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/33333>

50. Хасанова Шахноза Баходировна. (2024). ФИЛОСОФСКАЯ ПРИРОДА ЛИРИКИ И. АННЕНСКОГО. МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА, 2(5), 258–267. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11188698>

51. Хасанова Шахноза Баходировна. (2024). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЗМОВ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ПРОИЗНОШЕНИЮ, ГРАММАТИКЕ, ЛЕКСИКЕ И ПЕРЕВОДУ. МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА, 2(4), 431–440. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10968956>

52. Хасанова, Ш. (2024). PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(4), 128–133. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10936168>

53. Баходировна, Х. Ш. . (2024). Из Истории Изучения Пословиц И Поговорок. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 46, 513–520. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/2892>

54. Хасанова, Ш. (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10651477>. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(2), 425–435. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10651477>

55. Xasanova, S. (2024). DIFFERENCE BETWEEN PROVERB AND SAYING. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(1), 140–147. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10467418>

56. Xasanova, S., & murodova, D. (2023). REPRESENTATION OF THE SYSTEMIC RELATIONS OF RUSSIAN VOCABULARY IN PROVERBS AND SAYINGS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 276–280. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24346>

57. Xasanova, S. (2023). USING EXPRESSIVE VOCABULARY IN RUSSIAN PROVERBS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 403–408. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/25248>

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 6, 30 Июнь

58. Hasanova, S. (2023). SYSTEM RELATIONS IN THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE VOCABULARY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 72–74. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/23900>
59. Баходировна, Х. Ш. (2023). Гендерная Лексика В Русском Языке. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 2(11), 324–331. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/ijfe/article/view/1505>
60. Хасанова Шахноза Баходировна. (2023). РЕПРЕЗЕНТАЦИЯ СИСТЕМНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ РУССКОЙ ЛЕКСИКИ В ПОСЛОВИЦАХ И ПОГОВОРКАХ. *International journal of education, social science & humanities. finland academic research science publishers*, 11(4), 1220–1226. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7847968>
61. Xasanova, S. (2023). STRUCTURAL – SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PROVERBS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(12), 619–625. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/27109>
62. Nigmatova Gulnoz Khamidovna, & Khasanova Shakhnoza Bakhodirovna. (2022). System Relations in the Vocabulary of the Russian Language. *Global Scientific Review*, 3, 44–48. Retrieved from <https://www.scienticreview.com/index.php/gsr/article/view/22>
63. Shaxnoza Baxadirovna, X. (2023). PROVERBS IN THE LEXICOGRAPHICAL ASPECT. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 2(12), 429–437. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/ijfe/article/view/1771>
64. Xasanova, S. (2024). DIFFERENCE BETWEEN PROVERB AND SAYING. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 140–147. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/27853>
65. Xasanova, S. (2024). NAMES OF PERSONS IN RUSSIAN, UZBEK PROVERBS AND SAYINGS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 425–435. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/29049>
66. Хасанова, Ш. Б. (2023). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ВЫРАЗИТЕЛЬНЫХ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЕЙ ЛЕКСИКИ В РУССКИХ ПОСЛОВИЦАХ. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 403–408. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/25248>